

A critical review of social scientific research on carbon capture and storage

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Carbon capture and storage
Transformation
Social variables
Critical review
Artificial intelligence
Participation

ABSTRACT

Carbon capture and storage technologies have become a prominent discussion point within the broader portfolio of mitigation options to limit climate warming to well below 2 °C. Most carbon capture and storage research has focused on technical and economic aspects. However, there is a growing recognition of the systemic nature of sustainability transitions and the importance of diverse societal considerations. Despite this emerging focus, the research field is constrained by persistent assumptions.

This critical scoping review of social scientific research on carbon capture and storage analysed 108 research articles. Using a combination of manual and artificial intelligence coding, the analysis focused on identifying social variables. The review identified three key themes: acceptance, engagement and participation, and governance and policy.

Social scientific research on carbon capture and storage has been dominated by an acceptance-awareness paradigm and a tendency to view the public solely as actors impacted by the transition. Normative questions have received limited attention, though new interest is emerging. These paradigms and identified research gaps suggest that the field has adopted a transition perspective rather than a transformation perspective. By discussing the differences between these perspectives, this review provides a novel understanding of the research field, which can support socially sustainable development as carbon capture and storage momentum grows. Additionally, the review explores the advantages and challenges of employing artificial intelligence tools in qualitative social sciences.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
TAK	Titles, abstracts, and keywords

1. Introduction

Carbon capture and storage (CCS) refers to a suite of technologies, which can play a part in climate change mitigation and sustainability transitions. CCS has a long history, and it was first considered as a mitigation technology already in 1977 [1]. CCS often refers to CO₂ (carbon dioxide) capture at large point sources, such as power plants or industrial facilities [2]. The captured CO₂ is compressed and transported to be injected into deep geological formations for permanent storage [2]. This permanent storage requires continuous monitoring. CO₂ can also be

captured straight from the atmosphere using direct air capture or from bioenergy processes. The captured CO₂ can also be utilised instead of stored. This review focuses on carbon capture from large point sources and CO₂ storage. The debates and social considerations on carbon capture and utilisation, direct air capture, bioenergy with CCS and carbon capture from large point sources are different [3].

CCS has been a contested technology. A special report on CCS by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change in 2005 [4] initiated a wave of interest in CCS as a climate mitigation solution. However, CCS failed to deliver on the initial hype [5,6]. From 2008 onwards significant opposition started to emerge towards CO₂ storage projects, especially in the Netherlands, Germany, Denmark, and the US, contributing to the cancellation of projects [7]. Additionally, a range of economic and political barriers and uncertainty contributed to the slow uptake of CCS [5, 8,9]. In recent years, the momentum for CCS has been growing again as the International Energy Agency's Sustainable Development Scenario in 2022 allocated CCS a crucial role in achieving greenhouse gas emissions reduction goals [10]. The European Commission has also been

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.115063>

Received 12 September 2023; Received in revised form 17 June 2024; Accepted 27 October 2024

Available online 5 November 2024

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developing a policy framework to better support carbon capture implementation in Europe [11]. Simultaneously, some argue that CCS is an expensive distraction from oil and gas phase-out instead of the crucial solution to climate change mitigation [12]. Exploring the social dimension of CCS is crucial for aligning diverse interests and ensuring that its implementation aligns with climate goals and societal needs and complexity.

Social sciences have an important, but sometimes underappreciated, role in sustainability transitions [13–16]. While most CCS research has concentrated on technical and economic aspects, the contributions from social sciences, though present, remain limited in scope. Previous reviews of social scientific research on CCS [9,17,18] have showcased that a majority of the research has focused on social acceptance and stakeholder attitudes. Existing research has also highlighted some key areas where social sciences could better contribute to CCS development, such as co-creation [19], justice [20], trade-offs [17], and participation [21]. Buck [17] has argued that the existing social sciences insights have not been adopted in practice. These limitations discussed in previous reviews are brought together in this review to discuss some of the underlying paradigms that provide an explanation for the research gaps as well as an avenue to broaden the research field.

Critical social sciences perspectives have been even more underappreciated in sustainability transitions [22] and are almost absent from social scientific research on CCS. Despite some emerging interest, critical research on CCS remains rare, and therefore this review aims to contribute to these critical discussions. Taking a critical perspective on sustainability transformations can be understood as “going beyond the identification of toolkit-style solutions to environmental crisis to provide context, framings, approaches, and reflection on societal transformation” [23]. A key element of critical approaches is this scrutinising of the underlying meanings, structures, and institutions that resist change [24, 25]. Critical perspectives play a crucial role in implementing research insights into practice. Without a critical perspective, it is challenging to identify the underlying structures that hinder these processes. When critically considering sustainability transitions, it becomes evident that justice, power, and participation are interconnected and crucial aspects [22,23,26]. Sustainability transitions inherently involve value-based questions and cannot be separated from normative considerations [27]. To give due attention to these considerations, this review focuses on the critical social scientific research on CCS and therefore pays special attention to the topics of justice, power, and participation.

This critical scoping review analyses 108 social scientific articles on CCS using a combination of manual and artificial intelligence coding. The main objective of this review is to identify key variables within social scientific research on CCS and pinpoint areas that necessitate further investigation. The primary research question is: What is the current state of understanding, and research gaps in social scientific research on CCS? To provide a deeper understanding of the key gaps and paradigms of the research field, the review will also look at: What is the role of justice, participation, and power dynamics in social scientific research on CCS? The analysis resulted in the identification of three key themes: (1) acceptance, (2) engagement and participation; and (3) governance and policy.

The previous reviews of social scientific research on CCS have suggested different categorisations. Markusson et al. (2012) divided the literature into two broad themes, economics-focused research, and research focusing on public understanding and acceptance [28]. Ashworth et al. (2015) divided the literature into four broad categories (1) “assessment and concerns of the general public”, (2) “assessment and concerns of key stakeholders”, (3) “assessment of the role of communication style and content”, and (4) “assessment of experiences from real-life projects” [29]. L’Orange Seigo et al. (2014) identify several key concepts important specifically for public perceptions of CCS [18]. Buck (2021) on the other hand focused on whether existing social scientific research on CCS applies to the current context, whether it has been utilised in practice, and what social scientific research on CCS should be conducted

in the future [17].

This review adopts a novel approach by directly linking social scientific research on CCS to the framework of sustainability transitions research. The review moves beyond merely identifying research gaps to interrogating the underlying assumptions that have shaped the field. Unlike previous reviews, which often conflated social scientific research on CCS with social acceptance research, this review adopts a broader, more systemic perspective. The review scrutinises how entrenched paradigms have influenced the research landscape and explores how the field can evolve to better address contemporary challenges. Given the significant changes in the context for CCS, since most previous reviews were conducted, this review provides a timely reassessment, questioning established paradigms and suggesting pathways for future research that align with sustainability transitions.

To bring the social scientific research on CCS discussion to the context of sustainability transitions, the results of the review will be compared to a framework introduced by Sovacool et al. (2020) [14]. Their work identified three main domains for sociotechnical research on energy and climate: (1) sociotechnical systems, (2) policy, and (3) expertise and publics (Fig. 1). This comparison highlights how limited attention to normative elements, a focus on social acceptance and a narrow role for the public have shaped social scientific research on CCS, indicating that the research has adopted a transition instead of a transformation perspective.

This review provides four key contributions. First, it identifies social CCS variables, offering a comprehensive and up-to-date perspective on the various types of social scientific research conducted on CCS. Second, it identifies gaps in the research field. Third, it contributes to critical social sciences discussion on CCS by analysing and discussing what paradigms have shaped the research field. Last, it contributes to the methodological debate on the use of AI for qualitative social sciences.

Section Two will explain the literature review strategy. Section Three presents the results of the analysis and explanations of the three themes. Section Four discusses the key paradigms of the research field and how it has often departed from a transition rather than a transformation perspective. Last, Section Five concludes the review.

2. Methods

A scoping review was selected as the review method to investigate social scientific research on CCS, to identify variables and knowledge gaps, and to scope the research field [30,31]. Scoping reviews take a broad approach, focusing on mapping literature and answering broader research questions [31]. Systematic reviews focus on more precise questions and are more fixed in their approach [31].

Science Direct was chosen as the search tool due to its accessibility, and ability to conduct well-refined searches, which was advantageous for conducting a scoping review on an ambiguous concept. Additionally, Science Direct is particularly suitable for social concepts as it has a large database of social sciences and humanities journals and books.

The literature search was undertaken in two stages. Table 1 provides details of the literature search strategy. First, a search was conducted with terms: ‘social’ and ‘societal’. To ensure a focus on the most relevant articles, searches were performed across titles, abstracts, and keywords (TAK). Additionally, to specifically target the societal aspects of CCS, searches with more than 40 results were further refined by applying the social sciences subject area filter. The first literature search step indicated limited research on justice, participation, and power, and a prevalence of social acceptance, attitudes and perceptions, and communication research. The second step of the literature search focused on these topics with six more search terms: power, justice, participation, public, social acceptance, and support (second stage, Table 1). The scope of ‘social’ can include diverse topics, and these additional search terms were chosen inductively based on the initial research collected and the critical social sciences focus. As such the research approach is abductive. As the language used by authors varies,

Fig. 1. Adaptation of the Figure “Overview of main domains and topics of STS energy and climate research”. Source: [14].

Table 1
Literature search strategy. Source: Authors.

	Search term	N	Further revision? N	Date of search
First stage	social AND “carbon capture” in TAK	229	Further revision with a focus on social sciences: n = 28	09/03/2023
	social AND “CO ₂ capture” in TAK	25	No	09/03/2023
	societal AND “carbon capture” in TAK	48	Further revision with a focus on social sciences: n = 7, also a review of all 48 results to make sure no significant results were missed.	09/03/2023
Second stage	societal AND “CO ₂ capture” in TAK	5	No	09/03/2023
	power AND “carbon capture” in TAK	2763	Further revision with a focus on social sciences: n = 48	09/03/2023
	power AND “CO ₂ capture” in TAK	2181	Further revision with a focus on social sciences: n = 14	09/03/2023
	justice AND “carbon capture” in TAK	11	No	09/03/2023
	justice AND “CO ₂ capture” in TAK	1	No	09/03/2023
	participation AND “carbon capture” in TAK	32	No	09/03/2023
	participation AND “CO ₂ capture” in TAK	6	No	09/03/2023
	public AND “carbon capture” in TAK	369	Further revision with a focus on social sciences: n = 36	09/03/2023
	public AND “CO ₂ capture” in TAK	57	Further revision with a focus on social sciences: n = 2	09/03/2023
	“social acceptance” AND “carbon capture” in TAK	34	No	09/03/2023
	“social acceptance” AND “CO ₂ capture” in TAK	2	No	09/03/2023
	support AND “carbon capture” in TAK	712	Further revision with a focus on social sciences: n = 40	09/03/2023
support AND “CO ₂ capture” in TAK	649	Further revision with a focus on social sciences: n = 0	09/03/2023	

searches were conducted with both ‘CO₂ capture’ and ‘carbon capture’ terms.

The searches resulted in 291 articles. To enable qualitative analysis,

the articles were screened for relevance and duplicates were removed. Research focusing solely on carbon capture and utilisation and carbon removal were also removed from the dataset due to the differences in societal considerations and debates [3]. After the screening process, the number of articles in the review totalled 107. These articles were further assessed for eligibility and 36 papers that did not include a significant social focus were removed from the dataset. Following a common practice with scoping reviews, the reference lists of the selected articles were reviewed for further research and 37 papers were added to the dataset. The research collected through the snowball method was chosen based on their importance as key sources of information that had not been adequately covered in the previously collected research. This resulted in the final number of articles being 108. Fig. 2 illustrates the scoping review process, following a modification of the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses for scoping reviews [31].

The analysis focused on the identification of social CCS variables, key concepts and objects of study in social scientific research on CCS. The data was coded and analysed with the help of Atlas.ti, a qualitative data analysis software. The initial codes were identified inductively, through a thorough reading of the articles (n = 110). The codes were grouped up (n = 19) to derive the themes for the research field. After the initial analysis, the initial findings were compared to the reviews found in the data. During the analysis process, Atlas.ti introduced AI coding tools, fuelled by OpenAI’s GPT model. A second round of coding was undertaken with the AI tools, to evaluate the use of these tools in social sciences and to make the analysis of a larger number of articles possible while not sacrificing the depth of analysis.

OpenAI’s ChatGPT model was introduced on November 30, 2022. ChatGPT has received a lot of attention in academic debates, especially on its use in and impact on education, while the research methodology dimension of this technology has received less attention. The integration of AI into data analysis software raises ethical and methodological considerations, which may lag behind AI’s rapid development. Atlas.ti’s AI tools are among the methodological tools introduced based on the ChatGPT model.

Social scientists have lagged behind with the rapid advancements in AI [32]. At the same time, social sciences have a crucial role in AI’s ethical and philosophical development [33], especially when it comes to the use of these tools in research. This indicates a gap between the rapid AI development and the integration of these tools into social sciences. Some of the key debates for the development of AI as a research methodology include the use of sensitive data and the ownership of data [34, 35]. Other key debates are related to the use of AI for academic writing and how that may impact the accuracy of information as some of the AI models are known to fabricate information. Overall, the use of AI comes with many methodological considerations as some of the control is shifted from the researcher to the AI.

Fig. 2. Scoping review process flow chart. Adapted from Ref. [31].

Atlas.ti introduced the AI coding tools in March 2023. The versions of the AI coding used for the analysis of this review were beta versions, and the software has gone through multiple updates since the introduction of the AI tools. The AI coding provides automatic open and descriptive coding. The process allows for transparency and human oversight. In this study, AI coding was combined with manual coding to ensure that possible AI-created errors, such as missing topics or incorrect interpretations, were limited.

The advantages of the AI tools include the precision of the coding, which supported the inclusion of a larger number of articles. The AI coding was very detailed, providing a level of rigorosity difficult with manual coding but at the same time making it more difficult to synthesise the codes. The AI-coding tool resulted in 2473 codes in 108 documents. The codes included detail that would have taken months, if not years, for a human to produce but took only hours for the AI. At the same time, the tool did not provide an option to focus the coding on the topic of interest, and as such many of the codes were irrelevant. Many of the codes were also synonyms of each other.

To begin limiting the number of codes, first, the codes with fewer than two quotations were removed. Then codes outside the scope of the review were deleted and synonym codes were merged. The AI analysis did not always differentiate or recognise different contexts, such as participation in decision-making processes and participation in research interviews. Furthermore, the AI tools were in beta version and had some technical limitations. For example, the program would sometimes crash in the middle of the coding process, and it was not possible to analyse all of the articles due to formatting limitations. The sorting process resulted

in the final number of codes being 502. These codes were further synthesised by dividing them into code groups (47). The AI-created codes were compared to and combined with the initial manual coding. The codes broadly aligned and resulted in the same themes. The main difference between the codes was the precision of the coding, with the manual codes being broader categories.

This experience highlighted the need to complement AI analysis with preliminary manual analysis to ensure rigour at least while the AI tools are still developing. Using AI for coding was time-consuming due to the need for close researcher oversight. This raises doubts about AI's ability to save time, often considered one of its main advantages. At the same time, the process highlighted less dominant topics, increasing the accuracy of the analysis. In summary, this review suggests a cautious approach to utilising the new AI tools in qualitative social sciences while emphasising the importance of integrating social science insights into AI development, especially as a methodological tool. The fast AI development calls for critical methodological discussions on its benefits and challenges. AI can provide significant methodological benefits which should be utilised in social sciences.

The specific literature search strategy and the use of the novel AI analysis method resulted in some research limitations. The qualitative focus of this review necessitated a selective approach to the dataset. As a result, the dataset may not provide a fully representative view of the entire research field. Social scientific research on CCS encompasses a larger body of work. For instance, Buck [17] estimated the existence of at least 150 peer-reviewed articles on the social dimension of CCS, and that this could increase further with a more holistic approach. Search in

Science Direct on July 5, 2023 with the search term: “carbon capture and storage” OR “CO₂ capture and storage” in TAK with the social sciences filter resulted in 134 results. Nevertheless, the initial literature search using the terms ‘social’ and ‘societal’ encompasses a broad range of social scientific research on CCS, supporting the overall findings and enabling some generalisations based on the findings of this review.

The use of AI coding tools in research is still relatively untested and unproven, which increases the risk of methodological errors. However, to mitigate this risk, we initially employed manual coding to ensure accuracy and reliability. Another limitation of this study arises from the rapid advancement of AI technology. The analysis was conducted in March 2023, and since then, AI tools have undergone significant development. As a result, the methodologies and capabilities of AI tools available at the time of this study may not reflect the most current advancements.

3. Social scientific research on carbon capture and storage

3.1. Social CCS variables

The key variables of social scientific research on CCS identified through the analysis can be summarised into three categories: (1) acceptance; (2) governance and policy; and (3) engagement and participation.

Social scientific research on CCS has evolved from a focus on CCS as a mitigation tool for fossil fuel power plants to CCS as a way to decarbonise energy-intensive industries [36], to remove carbon from the atmosphere [37] or to be used in hydrogen production [38]. Buck [17] has argued that the older social scientific research on CCS may have lost some of its relevance due to this change in context, further highlighting a need for rethinking the social dimension of CCS. Two shifts have been identified in the research, a shift from acceptance to a more nuanced analysis of the social, political, ethical, and governance context [19], and a shift from acceptance to communication [39]. The analysis identified both shifts, although the communication shift has been more

prominent. In the collected studies, research focusing on acceptance and perceptions was the most common way to approach the social dimension of CCS. From this, it can be concluded that the widely recognised [9,17] acceptance and stakeholder attitudes focus remains, although some changes are discernible.

The research has a wide geographical scope, but it also exhibits significant gaps. The most commonly analysed areas in the collected literature include the United Kingdom [40,41], the Netherlands [42,43], Australia [44,45], China [46,47], Germany [48,49], multiple European countries or Europe as a whole [50,51], USA [52,53], Sweden [54], Scotland [40,55], and Japan [56,57]. The research scope shows a limitation when it comes to research in the Global South, which has been highlighted by others as well [39,58].

The following sections will discuss in more detail some of the key insights from social scientific research on CCS and identify key gaps and debates. Fig. 3 visualises the key variables and categories of social scientific research on CCS.

3.2. Acceptance

The acceptance theme represents the most prominent way the social dimension of CCS has been approached. This category is characterised by a focus on public and stakeholder attitudes and perceptions, acceptance of CCS, and the diverse aspects impacting these. The acceptance theme broadly correlates with the topics: “the diffusion of low-carbon innovations”, and “public engagement and deliberation” in the Sovacool et al. [14] framework. CCS has been a controversial technology and gaining social acceptance has been one of the key social challenges for CCS deployment [9,17]. Many arguments have been raised both in favour and against CCS [59]. The main arguments in favour of CCS revolve around its potential to decrease greenhouse gas emissions in hard-to-abate sectors and avoid some of the societal upheaval of a deep transition [52,57]. On the contrary, the fact that CCS involves the opportunity for a less transformative transition and a risk of carbon lock-in and path dependency have been some of the main reasons to oppose CCS

Fig. 3. Social CCS variables. Source: Authors.

[59–61]. The challenges CCS has faced in achieving social acceptance have been raised as another key argument against CCS, as this showcases that it is not always a socially accepted climate mitigation approach [59].

Social acceptance has been understood in several ways, with significant differences in the approaches to studying social acceptance. Some researchers have examined social acceptance using positivistic approaches, with the goal of quantifying the degree to which the general public or local communities accept certain technologies, projects, or aspects of projects. While this is the dominant method for assessing social acceptance, it is important to recognise that social acceptance encompasses additional dimensions [62–64]. Quantitative positivistic methods, commonly adopted in the literature to investigate social acceptance [65–69], involve significant limitations in being able to incorporate the complexity of social processes and going beyond linear causality [70]. The positivistic research approach also includes the assumption that all research should be apolitical and value-free, which ignores the political context which plays an important part in the decisions about which research approach is appropriate [71]. When discussing social acceptance it is important to understand the diversity of the research that can be done using the concept [63,64].

The acceptance of CCS research has often focused on the acceptance, perceptions and attitudes of the public towards CCS, but it has also included research that uses broader conceptualisations of acceptance [21,49]. Attention has been paid not only to the acceptance of individual projects [43], but also to the acceptance of international collaboration on CO₂ storage [72] and CCS in general [73–75], and acceptance by stakeholders beyond the public [8,76,77]. Diverse factors have been identified to impact the social acceptance of CCS. These factors are deeply connected and take different meanings and importance depending on context. Some of these connections are visualised in Fig. 4, but the interconnections are more complex than can be illustrated in a simple figure. Many studies have only focused on certain factors, leading to an oversimplification of the complex relationship between technology and its acceptance. For instance, Oltra et al. [78] have emphasised that lay perceptions are more complex than often assumed.

CCS acceptance research showcases a dominant awareness-acceptance paradigm, reasoning that increasing awareness is key to

acceptance. Acceptance has often been connected to the awareness of climate change and CCS technology [79–82]. This has fuelled research interest in CCS communication [39,83]. Otto and Gross [39] have investigated CCS communication and argue that even though the research focus is moving away from the acceptance logic, it still retains a persuasion undertone. The communication research appears to rely on the assumption that increasing awareness will increase acceptance. Some of the other research highlighted that this assumption may not be accurate and that providing more information may have a limited impact on acceptance [84]. This alternative perspective also raises questions about whose knowledge is accepted as legitimate, which was discussed in a few of the articles with the concept of the deficit-framing approach [17,84] and epistemic justice [39]. Other interconnected key factors for gaining acceptance include trust [68,85], benefit and risk perception [51], and participation [21,81]. These have been some of the most associated factors for social acceptance of CCS. Still, the number of factors influencing social acceptance identified in the research field is vast, as visualised in Fig. 4.

Social acceptance has been the most common theme in social scientific research on CCS. This research has focused on several variables to explain how acceptance is formed and how it may be fostered. At the same time, it has rarely taken a holistic approach to this, and has focused only on some of the variables [with some notable exceptions: 18,64]. Social acceptance of CCS research has been strongly shaped by an awareness-acceptance paradigm.

3.3. Engagement and participation

The participation and engagement theme is connected to the “*expertise and publics*” dimension of the Sovacool et al. (2020) [14] framework. New interest in participation and engagement in the context of CCS is emerging. Still, in most cases, it would be more accurate to speak only of engagement. The research largely does not discuss the possibility of the public having a more active role in CCS implementation. Participation and engagement were often used without distinction between the two in the analysed research. Van Os et al. [21] argue that the importance of participation is recognised by the key stakeholders but it often focuses on information provision. This follows the underlying

Fig. 4. Social acceptance of CCS variables. Source: Authors.

logic that the lack of information is the main reason for public attitudes toward CCS.

In general, the importance of local community engagement in CCS projects is recognised in the research [39,86–88]. The research also provides many recommendations on best practices for engagement [86, 89] as well as the connected activity of communication [90–92]. Some of the latest research also argues for more active participation of the public and communities in decision-making processes [88,93]. Kuch [93] argues that the public could be a site of deliberation and contestation of issues. A study by ter Mors and van Leeuwen [88], published after the data collection, emphasises that communities must be involved in the CCS decision-making processes. Their study highlights how public engagement should result in their views being genuinely taken into consideration in decision-making processes, and how giving the public a pseudo-voice is as damaging as giving them no voice [88]. Otto et al. [94] emphasise the connection between participation and trust. Otto and Gross [39] argue that the dominant justification for CCS relies on arguments which have not been discussed with the public. Four of the analysed articles also advocate for a dialogue approach where the diverse perspectives and knowledge claims of actors are taken seriously [39,81,87].

In summary, the importance of public engagement is recognised in social scientific research on CCS. Still, in most of the research, the scope of the participation discussion is limited, and the public is not envisioned to have a more active role in CCS implementation beyond being actors impacted by the processes.

3.4. Governance and policy

The governance and policy theme has received the least attention in social scientific research on CCS. This theme is most clearly connected to the dimension *policy* in the Sovacool et al. [14] framework. One of the main reasons why the governance and policy theme has received less attention is because CCS is still an emerging technology. The fossil fuel dependence of society has not only enabled but also defined and limited socio-technical systems and their future [28, p. 3]. As CCS is embedded in the issue of fossil fuel dependency, this raises important questions about how CCS should be governed and what pathways should be pursued. Some of this discussion has been undertaken in social scientific research on CCS, but many questions about governance, power and politics remain under-explored. With the recently growing momentum and the introduction of new CCS goals and ambitions [11], addressing governance and policy questions has become imperative.

Justice is an emerging topic in social scientific research on CCS but remains under-investigated. This can be seen for example through the literature search (Table 1), which resulted in only 12 results (note the specific search strategy). The emerging research has discussed topics such as epistemic justice [93], the role of CCS in climate conflicts [95], and the potential of CCS to contribute to a just transition [20,60,96]. Investigating the global North-South divide is especially relevant for CCS as the global North has received most of the benefits from fossil fuels and CCS provides an opportunity for the Global South to receive some of the same benefits [59,97]. At the same time, continuous investment in and use of fossil fuels is not a desirable option and comes with many related considerations such as the capacity building of actors in the Global South [58]. Still, only a small number of studies have focused on the global North-South questions [39,58]. This increased interest in the justice dimensions of CCS is further elaborated by Buck [17] who identifies justice as a key element of future social sciences CCS research. The emerging research has indicated diverse justice implications related to CCS implementation.

CCS has been recognised as an opportunity to study controversy, conflict, and the politicisation of technology, and to question to what degree the established social structures and practices are challenged [28], [98]. Nevertheless, the research on power dynamics and critical approaches remains limited. Power dynamics were not a common

research topic in the analysed research. However, some of the critical articles still contribute to these discussions, even though they did not explicitly identify as doing so. The critical research scrutinises the deficit framing of the public [84,93], how CCS can exacerbate climate conflict [95], and the influence and shared perceptions of the global CCS community [99]. The topic of imaginaries, frames, and narratives represents research on how the perceptions of actors are influenced, and this has received significant attention in the research field [100,101]. However, when perceptions of CCS are studied, this is often done from an acceptance perspective, and not from a more fundamental critical perspective.

CCS has been connected to the idea of ecological modernisation, meaning that instead of challenging the underlying power dynamics and aiming towards a more comprehensive societal transformation, the approach is rather technocratic [98]. A key element of this is framing CCS as a technological fix to climate change [93,97]. CCS has the allure of providing an end-of-pipe solution that allows the current fossil regime to remain largely intact, and the fossil fuel industry has been a driving force for CCS [97]. Additionally, the utilisation of captured carbon for Enhanced Oil Recovery has been one of the initial driving forces for CCS deployment, and it has been central in making CCS financially viable, especially in the US [52,102]. At the same time, from a decarbonisation perspective, CCS only addresses the symptoms of an unsustainable fossil system, not its causes, resulting in a fundamental conflict. CCS (and other related technology) debates have been argued to be impacted by the fossil fuel industry [50] and CCS projects driven by fossil fuel world views instead of policy and participation [93]. On the contrary, for example, Ayasama & Ishii [57] argue that CCS provides a political glue that can align the competing interests between climate policy communities and fossil energy interest groups.

The governance and politics of CCS have received some research attention [98,103–105]. Still, the analysed studies did not provide a clear answer to how CCS is or should be governed, beyond giving information on some elements of the governance processes. These included the role of CCS in supporting collaborative action and the need for capacity building in developing countries [58], an analysis of differences between policy options [106], and an analysis of the governance processes of a failed CCS project [107]. This review does not conclude whether CCS policy has received sufficient research attention but policy was not a common focus in the collected research [some notable exceptions: 89,91]. The research on CCS has highlighted that policy frameworks play a crucial role in CCS implementation [106]. As CCS is an emerging technology with growing momentum, the demand for policy research insights is imperative. For example, the EU is increasing its efforts in CCS [11], highlighting the need for informed policies.

One form of governance which has been envisioned for CCS is ethical governance [39,93], and this is connected to the emerging interest in justice. Ethical governance is a form of governance which aims to integrate ethical considerations and moral issues into decision-making processes. Kuch [93] has argued that this includes taking seriously the knowledge claims of multiple actors and that governing fossil fuels ethically is especially challenging. Otto & Gross [39] discuss ethical governance and argue that stating that CCS is the only way to achieve deep emission cuts without significant societal upheaval marginalises those who do not agree. This framing of CCS as inevitable is one of the key examples of how the CCS discussions are embedded in power dynamics, further highlighting why further attention should be paid to these dynamics. The fossil fuel industry is a significant component of economic activities and assets in wealthy countries. As a result, the industry has a dominant role in shaping future perspectives for society, raising the question of who has the authority to determine which technologies are inevitable.

In conclusion, the governance and policy theme includes many variables but is the least investigated theme in the analysed social scientific research on CCS. The theme includes significant gaps when it comes to the topics of justice, power dynamics, and governance

approaches. The research displays an emerging interest in the theme, and most of the research discussing justice, governance, and power dynamics was published after 2017.

4. Key insights and research gaps: it has been all about transition instead of transformation

The key insights from the review can be summarised as follows. Social scientific research on CCS has been shaped by an acceptance-awareness paradigm and a tendency to see the public as actors only impacted by the transition. The latest research showcases an emerging attention to broader and normative questions, but this research still remains limited. Many of these findings are not completely new to CCS research, but this review brings them together and identifies and questions some of the underlying beliefs and paradigms. The analysis of the gaps and their underlying paradigms point to a transition instead of a transformation perspective on the study of CCS. This will be elaborated on in this section.

The framework provided by Sovacool et al. [14] is reflected here as a point of comparison to the identified CCS social variables to tease out the key features and gaps of the research field. The three dimensions introduced by Sovacool et al. [14] (sociotechnical systems, policy, and expertise and publics) broadly correspond with the identified social CCS variables. Expertise and publics have received significant research attention in social scientific research on CCS in the form of social acceptance, public engagement, and communication research. The other dimensions however received less attention, which leads us to conclude that there are significant gaps in the research field. Comparison of the topics of the Sovacool et al. framework and the social CCS variables highlighted that the topics: “(1) *power, social identity, and justice*; (2) *actors, networks, and heterogenous systems*; (3) *transforming innovation*; (4) *governing complex transitions*; (5) *global disparities and hegemony*; (6) *and expertise and democracy*”, were under-represented or absent from the analysed research. This, in turn, highlights specific paradigms of the research field, which can be described through the difference between transition and transformation perspectives. Many of the analysed articles discuss CCS through a sociotechnical transitions perspective [108–110], but the word transformation is rarely even mentioned in the research (some exceptions [98,111]).

Transitions focus on societal sub-systems (such as energy, mobility, cities, or industry) and how change occurs through non-linear processes and relations between support and barriers [112]. The transition perspective focuses on change processes from one state of being to another [112]. The social scientific research on CCS has focused on an individual system (when the system perspective was adopted) instead of interconnected systems. A transformation perspective focuses on interconnected systems, societal change, and the patterns and outcomes of change, with the outcome focus being avoiding undesirable system change [112]. The words transition and transformation are sometimes used without distinction between the two, even though they are distinct in their perspectives on the depth of change. Both transition and transformation perspectives include analysis of the normative elements of change. However, this is more highlighted with the transformation perspective, which takes a broader perspective on system change (societal) and focuses on more fundamental questions about the nature of change. The discussion on transformation relates to the debates on how sustainability transitions can change society. These debates have received limited attention in social scientific research on CCS, and some paradigms appear to have guided this approach. This need for research that investigates the interconnections between sociotechnical change and societal change has been identified as an important future research avenue [14], and as this review indicates, this applies also to the question of CCS.

Most social scientific research on CCS appears to start from the assumption that CCS is desirable and inevitable and that the role of society is to be informed about CCS so that the technology is accepted,

and implementation is not resisted. A more critical stance would not take this starting point for granted and would involve the broader public in normative discussions around what potential future pathways could look like, and consequently, what the role of CCS might be in such pathways. In the first approach CCS comes first and society second, while in the latter approach society comes first and CCS second. A transition perspective assumes an incremental decarbonisation pathway with CCS as a technological fix that allows current systems to remain relatively intact. A transformation perspective allows for more fundamental change that keeps the option open of not relying (as much) on end-of-pipe solutions like CCS if other, more radical changes in sustainable production and consumption could be achieved.

Bidwell and Sovacool [113] highlight the tensions between social acceptance research and justice research in how they perceive the scope and depth of the necessary change [113]. Social acceptance research tends to take a reformist and incremental approach to the transition, where changes happen to the system to make it more sustainable but the underlying structures remain largely the same [113]. Justice research seeks social transformation and wants to reshape infrastructure and institutional arrangements [113]. A key element of the transitions and incremental change perspective is that power remains with the incumbent actors [113], which can be the case with CCS implementation as it is a potential tool to maintain the current power structures.

As discussed in the previous sections, power and justice are under-explored concepts in social scientific research on CCS. The issues of gender, race, income, and social justice for example were not discussed in the collected research, but research on these topics can be (and should be) part of the research agenda [14]. Justice is a fundamental element of achieving a socially, economically, and environmentally sustainable future [114], and CCS is not beyond these discussions. On the contrary, CCS discussions are embedded in power dynamics. The collected literature that discusses power dynamics, focuses on the power of elites, those holding disproportionate power, such as the fossil fuel industry [115] and advocacy coalitions [52]. Still, research on power remains limited despite the crucial role understanding power dynamics plays in sustainability transitions [22].

“If transdisciplinary sustainability research is to contribute to sustainability transitions, issues of power dynamics need to be understood and accounted for” [22].

CCS has often been framed as the opposite of a transformation, as a way to avoid a deep transformation of society, as it involves a promise of solving the climate problem without changing production and consumption patterns [93,98]. This element of CCS has been described as a paradigm of ecological modernisation, the main idea of which is that instead of challenging the hegemonic structures and questioning the power dynamics, ecological problems can be solved without transforming society as a whole [98]. This perspective may have contributed to why social scientific research on CCS has rarely discussed CCS from a transformation perspective, even though it has been argued that CCS conflicts are an especially fitting avenue for questioning underlying social structures and practices [98]. The proponents of CCS have argued that CCS can be a bridging technology which makes the transition possible [116]. This can be taken further to advocate that CCS is a part of creating the necessary conditions for sustainability transformation and is thus transformative. Regardless of whether CCS can be transformative or not, it is a crucial element of climate mitigation discussions. Therefore, the normative elements of CCS require further attention and CCS debates must be broadened to the level of transformation.

The prevalent understanding of the relationship between society and technology in the collected research connects CCS further to a transition rather than a transformation. The notion that technology and society are separate, with technology only impacting society and society reacting to technology is common [28]. This makes it hard to see how society shapes technology, and how the relationship between the two is more of a co-evolution [28]. A one-way flow view of the relationship between

technology and society means that the role of social sciences is more limited [28]. The prevalent understanding of technology and society as separate is also represented through the framing of CCS as a technical fix to the complex challenge of climate change [93]. The prevalence of this perspective is evident in how the social dimension of CCS is often approached by looking at public perceptions, attitudes, and acceptance. This shifts the focus to how CCS impacts the public, rather than considering how the public can influence CCS (beyond objecting) and how this relationship can be bidirectional.

The understanding of the relationship between technology and society adopted in social scientific research on CCS is especially evident through inspection of how participation is understood largely as one-sided engagement. This focus can be argued to be limited to the lowest levels of the participation ladder [117], with more involved forms of participation receiving less support. Van Os et al. [21] for example, argue that the involvement of the public in CCS decision-making processes is not seen as beneficial by all stakeholders. However, sustainability transitions research has advanced collaborative approaches and emphasises the need to involve the wider society in transitions which require system-wide change [118]. Sustainability transitions research has also advanced a broad understanding of how the public can become involved in transition processes, which goes far beyond the public being merely impacted by the transition [119].

Unlike other elements of societal decarbonisation, such as renewable energy (e.g., microgeneration), CCS does not provide as clear routes for more active public participation. Still, due to the unavoidable interconnectedness of technology with society, participation should not be automatically ignored in these processes. The ways in which the public can participate in the energy transition are diverse [119]. First, the public can become involved by changing their everyday behaviours, consumption, and practices [118]. This type of participation focuses on energy efficiency and relates to CCS as the less energy is consumed, the less climate mitigation needs to rely on solutions like CCS. Second, the public can become involved through participation in energy production (or other forms of sustainable action) [118]. Last, the public can become involved through participation in decision-making processes [118]. This last category is most clearly relevant for fostering more active public involvement in CCS on a broader scale.

Climate-neutral pathway scenarios [4,10] are very powerful in terms of that they are seen as authoritative expectations, despite the many uncertainties and limitations involved with CCS implementation. Different applications of carbon capture, storage and utilisation do not have equal climate benefit, especially going beyond 2030, or 2050 [120, 121]. This highlights questions around power and participation, whose visions of the future are seen as valid, who gets to define these scenarios, and how the public should be involved in these decisions. As many citizens are currently unaware of CCS, it seems that societies are making an implicit, unconscious decision on the role that CCS will play in decarbonisation pathways. Social scientific research on CCS has the potential to contribute to a more explicit discussion of the meaning that people attribute to CCS and the role it should have in sustainable societies.

CCS research has often put project implementation as the core problem instead of approaching the challenge from the perspective of society, approaching CCS as a societal issue. Problem definition has been impactful for CCS implementation [122]. Problems are social constructions, and are a way to change reality and how different issues are perceived [123,124]. Social scientific research on CCS has often defined any challenges to CCS deployment as the core challenge (e.g., social acceptance needs to be investigated because it can and has caused challenges to CCS deployment). This has guided the research approaches and how issues such as the role of the public are perceived. Approaching the challenge from a societal perspective and considering CCS within the context of fundamental transformation may lead to different research focuses and approaches.

5. Conclusions

This study critically reviews social scientific research on CCS and identifies three key themes: (1) acceptance, (2) engagement and participation, and (3) governance and policy. The review participates in critical discussions on the paradigms and gaps of the research field and argues that the research has often departed from a transition rather than a transformation perspective. The paper also contributes to the methodological debate of using AI in qualitative social sciences.

This review presents important insights from social scientific research on CCS, but it still has some limitations. The literature search and AI analysis method were designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the field, but it's important to note that they may not fully capture every aspect. Future research could aim for a more in-depth approach by using a broader range of search terms or by focusing solely on specific themes. Additionally, the rapid progress in AI technologies and the lack of methodological debate on the topic require further refinement of AI methodology.

The importance of critical CCS research continues to increase as decisions need to be made on whether CCS is pursued at a large scale, which applications of it are pursued, and what the role of CCS should be in climate change mitigation. Previously, Europe has been described as the "Valley of Death" for CCS [125] and CCS has not been able to reach the scope imagined for it [5]. Looking forward, CCS is designed to play a significant role in climate change mitigation [10,11]. Committing to large-scale CCS or avoiding a clear decision on this both have significant consequences [98,103]. This dilemma goes beyond social acceptance or techno-economic considerations. These questions connect to ethical and broader discussions about sustainability pathways.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly AI to improve the readability and language of the paper. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Senni Maatta reports financial support was provided by European Union.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (Project name: CaLby2030; grant number: 101075416). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The project is also supported by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

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Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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